

The Role of Strategic Entrepreneurship on Quality of Services in the Hotels of the Jordanian capital Amman

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to identify the role of strategic entrepreneurship on the quality of services in the hotels of the Jordanian capital Amman. A quantitative methodology was adopted, a questionnaire was distributed to gather data from all management levels for the (146) hotels in the Jordanian capital Amman. (328) surveys were analyzed using SPSS and Amos. The study concluded that the strategic entrepreneurship and its dimensions (innovation, creativity, Risk taking, Proactiveness) influenced (55%) of the whole impact on the quality of hotel services in the hotels of Amman. The main recommendations of the study were involving employees in the decision-making process, Providing previous models for creative employees, creating a research and development allocations, providing proactive plans to face systematic and nonsystematic risks, cooperating with competitors.

Keywords: Strategic Entrepreneurship, quality of services, Hotels, Jordan, Amman

1.Introduction

In Latin the word "Hospital" is used, while in French "Hostel", whereas "Hospite" is in Italian and in Arabic called "Khan", or "Locanda". Today the nomination "Hotel" is known worldwide for denoting a place that offers goods and services. The spread of hotels in the Middle East wasn't feasible since Arabs are known for their free hospitality (Abdul Kader, 2001). Hotel can be defined as a resort for travelers that provides a range of services such as accommodation, food, drink and health club for a specific value of money (Sarhan, 2011), Recent years have witnessed a clear and tangible interest in the tourism sector, by which hotels are considered the cornerstone of its services, it is their responsibility to provide best quality services to the tourist or visitor, to achieve satisfaction by the beneficiaries of these services and thus enable this sector to support the Jordanian economy with returns, In addition of making profits that help to continue at the same level. However, hotels are currently facing more rapid technological changes than ever before, challenging them to provide the service within the standards of quality to suit the requirements of customers, within the intense competition and life evolution. According to the statistics of the Jordanian Ministry of Tourism (2018), the income generated from tourism in 2018 was about (4) billion, and the hotel's sector contribution to the GDP was about (16%). That is classified as the second source of GDP. Hence the quality of hotel services is a very important element in the field for its linkage to human comfort. Hotel management is a major factor in sustaining the quality of hotel services provided to customers.

Economic development has become a concern for modern societies, that's why entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs these days are considered the backbone of evolution, they play an important role in improving the ability to exploit opportunities and create values in an accelerated and highly complex environment (Qurna, 2014). Entrepreneurship is seen As a savior for these organizations to support their continuity and achieve their goals, entrepreneurship strategies are modern methods, important and promising fields in developed and

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developing countries (Li et al., 2018), strategic entrepreneurship such as innovation, creativity, risk taking and initiation encourages the workers to take the decision, which will reflect positively on both their performance and motivation to continue exploiting the resources of the Organization to the best way and at the lowest cost. This study came to examine the impact of one of the modern economic and administrative concepts that participate in the economic development by maintaining the reputation of Jordanian hotels through the service provided to guests and beneficiaries using the resources wisely.

2. Research Problem

Annual report of the Jordanian Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities (Ministry of Tourism, 2017), the Association of Hotels (2017) and articles like (Khasawneh, 2017) and (Al-Sabeel, 2016), (Al-Rifai, 2019) stated that Jordanian hotel sector is unable of to keeping pace with developments manifested in low occupancy of hotel rooms and low demand on its services.

Reports also showed High job turnover and lack of expertise in the sector, especially in the sections of cleaning, kitchen, restaurant, and maintenance. And that effected the quality of service delivered to customers. The problem can be formulated by answering the following question: "

- What is the impact of strategic entrepreneurship with its dimensions (Innovation, Creativity, Risk taking, Initiation) on the quality of services in Amman hotels?"
- The following sub-questions are subdivided:
- What is the level of innovation strategy in Amman hotels?
- What is the level of innovation strategy in Amman hotels?
- What is the level of risk strategy in Amman hotels?
- What is the level of the strategy in the hotels in Amman?
- What is the quality of service in Amman hotels?
- Are there variances for the hotel rating variable in terms of service quality?

3. Research Hypothesis

H0: There is no statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for Strategic Entrepreneurship with its dimensions (innovation, creativity, risk, initiative) on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels.

H0-1: There is no statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the innovation strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels.

H0-2: There is no statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the creativity strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels.

H0-3: There is no statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the risk strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels.

H0-4: There is no statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the initiative strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels.

4. Study Significance

This study is one of the important studies linking strategic Entrepreneurship and quality of services in the Jordanian hotel sector, which is one of the important and vital sectors in Jordan.

Practical importance is also evident as this study provides decision-makers in this important service sector with advice and information and data necessary through its findings and recommendations and contribute to reflect the image of Jordan to the world.

5. Study Objectives

To achieve the main objective in the study aimed to:

- Develop a theoretical framework for strategic entrepreneurship and service quality.
- Identify the impact of strategic entrepreneurship on the quality of services in hotels in the Jordanian capital Amman.
- Develop a tool with psychometric properties to measure the relationship between study variables.
- Provide a set of recommendations and results to the decision-maker in the sector in question.

6. Research Methodology

To test the hypotheses of the study and answer its questions, the quantitative approach was followed by following the method of surveys to show the impact of strategic entrepreneurship on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels.

7. Study Limits

- The study was applied to hotels in the Jordanian capital Amman.
- This is a cross-sectional study, data was collected in the period from 1/02/2019 to 30/03/2019.
- The study targeted employees working at all administrative levels.

8. Study Limitations

The most difficulties were:

- 1 - Limited previous studies are linking strategic entrepreneurship and quality of services.
2. Difficulty in collecting data from the study population due to lack of cooperation from the targeted sector.

9. Study Sample

The number of employees working in the hotel sector according to reports of the Jordanian Hotel Association and the Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities was (9736), and the sample size was (370) according to the sample table (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). Predicted sample of employees was distributed as follows:

Hotel Rating	Number of Hotel	Number of Employees		Total	Sample Number of Employees		Total
		Males	Females		Males	Females	
5 Stars	17	5165	562	5727	196	21	218
4 Stars	22	1930	149	2079	73	6	79
3 Stars	38	1192	126	1318	45	5	50
2 Stars	38	418	65	483	16	2	18
1 Star	31	125	4	129	5	0	5
Total	146	8830	906	9736	336	34	370

Table 1 targeted Sample and population distribution

10. Study Instrument

The sources of data are two:

1. Secondary sources such as books, references, periodicals, articles, reports, previous studies at the center of the study, and reports of the Jordanian Hotel Association and the Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities.
2. Primary sources represented by a questionnaire designed as a main data collection tool, In this study, (370) paper and electronic questionnaires were distributed to all levels (upper, middle, lower) in hotels operating in the capital Amman, (340) distributed were retrieved, leaving (328) valid questionnaires that are acceptable (88.6%) which are acceptable according to (Babbie, 2011).

11. Literature Review

1. (Jassem, 2018) The study aimed to measure the role of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial thinking in enhancing the quality of service, the study population consisted of department's managers in (5) private Iraqi banks in the province of Najaf, data was collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using the SPSS program. The study found a statistically significant relationship between entrepreneurship and pioneering thinking on the quality of service. recommendations were to monitor the material and moral potential and through the exploitation of creative thinking (creativity, initiative, taking the risk, uniqueness) as possible, and to identify the shortcomings in the performance of the service provided through periodic questionnaires.

2. (Al-Taie, 2017) The study aimed to measure the impact of adopting entrepreneurial strategies (creativity, innovation, taking risk, initiative) and its role in achieving sustainable competitive advantage in its dimensions (Quality, Competitive Position, Information Technology, Strategic Flexibility) at Baghdad Soft Drinks Co. (48) questionnaires were distributed to a purposive sample of senior management and then the results of the data were analyzed using SPSS program. The study found a statistically significant role from entrepreneurial

strategies on Sustainable Competitive Advantage. The study recommended an emphasis on quality in the product and the diversification of production in terms of introducing unique products that distinguish them from competitors, which leads to the sustainability of excellence and leadership in the market.

3. (Hakim & Ali, 2017) The study aimed to clarify the impact of strategic entrepreneurship (taking risks, seizing opportunities, creativity, entrepreneurial culture) on an organization's development (organization, individuals, working groups). Data was collected from the Election Commission's 100 employees in the Independent High Electoral Commission of Iraq using the questionnaire. (76) questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed using the program (SPSS). The most prominent recommendations are the need to develop the skills and behavioral characteristics of senior and lower administrations, the division of duties and powers and work on spreading strategic entrepreneurship structure.

4. (Al-Hadrawi & Al-Kalabi, 2013) The study aimed at identifying the impact of the entrepreneurship orientation on the customer's perception of the quality of service. A sample consisting of (103) hotels was selected from (230) hotels in the Najaf governorate and 80 questionnaires were valid for statistical analysis using the SPSS program. The most important conclusion of the research is that the trend of hotels towards entrepreneurship was not at the required level and that led to a negative impact on the satisfaction of the customer's wishes, which indicates that there is no clear impact on the perception of the customer through the quality of service.

5. (Abadi, et al., 2010) The study aimed at recognizing the role of strategic entrepreneurship in formulating the entrepreneurial marketing strategy in business organizations in Pepsi Lab Kufa. The study targeted (20) senior managers. The study concluded that the leading organizations approach their customers by offering products for the first time or injecting an existing product in a new market. The study recommended that business organizations stimulate the entrepreneurial situation within the organization and educate employees about adopting entrepreneurial behavior and thus achieving a competitive advantage.

6. (Anwar, et al., 2018) The study aimed at examining the relationships between market adventure and intellectual capital and entrepreneurship strategy on the performance of new projects using the competitive advantage as a mediator in Rawal Yendi and Islamabad Pakistan. Data were collected from (227) projects through a structured questionnaire in addition to interviewing (17) entrepreneurs. The results of the study highlighted that intellectual capital, entrepreneurship strategy and competitive advantage have a significant positive impact on the performance of new projects. Similarly, intellectual capital The Entrepreneurial Strategy contributes positively to the competitive advantage, and the competitive advantage fully mediates the relationship between intellectual capital and the performance of new ventures, and plays a partial mediation role in the relationship between entrepreneurial strategy and the performance of new ventures.

7. (Ashraf, et al., 2018) This study aimed at measuring the impact of service quality, the image of the company and its perceived value on customer loyalty in the presence of customer satisfaction and absence. In the four service sectors: hospitals, education, banks and hotels in Pakistan. The data were collected by taking a non-probability sampling (snowball method). The questionnaire was used to collect the data. The most significant results were the confirmation of the role of mediation of customer satisfaction in the relationship between quality of service, brand loyalty, image and brand loyalty.

8. (Baregheh, et al., 2009) This study aimed at measuring the extent of innovation, which is a dimension of entrepreneurship in the UK small and medium food industries, the questionnaire was used in the collection of data distributed manually (221) A valid questionnaire for statistical analysis. The study found that gradual innovation is more applied than radical, product and process innovation received a higher degree of attention than packaging, the study found that companies are largely committed to the application of standards that stimulate innovation.

12.Literature Review

The modern term "Strategic entrepreneurship" is the result of combining two terms "management strategies" and "entrepreneurship", and both seek to accomplish the organizational goals (Venkataraman and Sarasvathy, 2001). According to Al-Hadrawi, (2011) researchers like Hybrid and Meyer considered them one concept.

Figure 1 Strategic Entrepreneurship

Fig. 1 shows how Entrepreneurship is obliged in offering the latest either in creating or renewing a current organization (Ireland and Webb, 2017)

The strategy:

Strategos or General or leader, which is rooted in the Greek lexicon "army" and "lead", this Greek term means planning to eliminate the enemy by the best resources Allocation (Bracker, 1980), It is important for the decision-maker to think of plans that help to maintain and implementing competitive advantages in the midst of this competition (Goetsch and Davis, 2014).

The importance of strategies was listed by (Idris Al, 2016) in nine points (1) Analysing the opportunities and threats in the organizational external environment (2) analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the internal environment of the organization, (3) formulating the functions and objectives of the organization, (4) Contributing in clarifying the organizational future vision that helps decision-making, (5) helping to estimate the amount of resources needed by the organization in the future, (6) Serving the organization in dealing with expected and unexpected challenges, (7) Providing the organization with the supporting capabilities to guide it in a competitive environment (8) classifying priorities and opportunities, (9) giving the Organization the ability to appropriately allocate Time and resources to deal with the opportunities.

Entrepreneurship:

This term is Derived from the French word *enteprendre*, firstly introduced in the World Trade Dictionary by Jacques des Bruslons in 1723 (Almubtaath, 2014). The first part *entre* means "intermediary" and the second part *prendre* means "taking" ,this term was used to name someone intermediating between the seller and buyer who bears a business starting risk, product or service (Bolton & Thompson, 2002). It is a way of thinking that focuses on opportunities, innovation and growth, and is found in large and non-profit organizations (Allen, 2006). Entrepreneurs invent new services, products and technology that over time dissipate existing products, services and technology and that was named as "intelligent destruction" (Schumpeter, 1934), They find organizations with new vision bearing the risk, and seize opportunities to add value using their resources (Shattock, 2005). The entrepreneurial organization is known for creating jobs and contributing positively in increasing the national income by bringing its products and services to the market with modern technology, plus it is central to development and innovation in the entrepreneurial process as a whole (Ireland, et... al, 2006, Manimala, 2006: 283). According to a study conducted by the International Labor Organization of the reason why women are gaining a bigger share as entrepreneurs is to flee from underestimating their abilities and

energies and also because of the glass ceiling that prevented them from senior management positions (Kephart & Schumacher, 2005). Entrepreneur's characteristics are summarized by (Bolton & Thompson, 2002) as follows (1) Entrepreneur makes the difference on the level of business as a whole, (2) they are creative and innovative and therefore they are a challenge to the giant business, (3) they also discover the opportunities that are overlooked. (4) They are creative in providing resources even if they beg, borrow or steal them when necessary, (5) they have good communication networks and they create teams that follow their plans. (6) Entrepreneurs are ready to deal with the emergence of crises that threatens the life of the organization and knows how to deal with risks and create challenges and find plans to overcome or deal with. (7) They control and pursue the business, even if they do not manage it tightly they significantly control it. (8) Entrepreneurs seek a long-term relationship with the customer, they think of a service or product that might come up completely different when applied because the customer-led this transformation. (9) They do not build their wealth on environmental tragedies, for example, destroying the countryside or cutting down trees or other resources.

Entrepreneurship is important and necessary for confronting the rapid changes in the surrounding environment, as they offer procedures and innovations as keys to deal with the intensity of competition that has Three reasons that can be summarized as (1) ease of market entry by new competitors, (2) Administrations trust Traditional methods (3) Skilled labor seek independence by creating competing organizations. (Chirani & Hasanzadeh, 2013). Entrepreneurship provides organizations (1) responds to changes quickly and accurately, (2) meets the needs of the customer and the consumer (3) maintains the organization's market share and seeks to expand, (4) Provides organizations flexibility to make them ready to learn, (5) Supports product's quality (6) Introduces new innovative outputs, (7) Encourages new markets invasion, (8) Secures appropriate revenues, (9) Encourages the independence of more units, (10) Activates human resources need. (Gesture, 2015).

Entrepreneurship dimensions:

Previous studies measured strategic management by many dimensions, the most frequent dimensions that (Jasim, 2018, Ashraf, et al., 2018, Hadrawi & Chelabi, 2013, Malik, et al., 2018, Raggad, et al., 2017, Al-Taie, 2017, Scarne, 2008, Akbaba, et al., 2006) agreed on are: Innovation, Creativity, Risk Taking, Initiation.

1. Innovation: Many do not distinguish between innovation and invention because they are strongly linked. The invention is the first appearance of a new idea, product or process while innovation is the commercial marketing of them (Fagerberg, 2004). Innovation by lexicography is to introduce something new or unknown that has just emerged aiming at creating value (Lahrou & Maaninou, 2018), innovation is the transformation of new ideas to revenues and profits. considering the continued acceleration and intense competition in global and local markets. It is difficult for researchers and economists to limit the types of innovation because their numbers are growing. (Norman & Verganti, 2014). According to (Pain,2011, Jones,2013) Innovation is classified in two ways:

A. By nature:

1. **Product Innovation:** Comes in the form of new service, new specification or a completely new product.
2. **Process Innovation:** Improving existing processes to reduce costs, improving outputs, and certainly raising quality or designing a new production process.
3. **Marketing Innovation:** Influencing elements of the marketing mix to contribute to organization and customer interaction.
4. **Organizational Innovation:** Organizational readiness to assist new ideas introduced by the effect of the behavior of individuals and groups.

B. By degree:

1. **Radical innovation:** Supplants a current business model and starts a new business completely different.
2. **Gradual innovation:** Improving an existing product from time to time.

2. Creativity:

Every innovation begins with a creative idea that transcends current boundaries such as customs, traditions, knowledge and technology. It is the integration of previous unlinked ideas to come up with a completely new idea that functions totally different (Anderson, 1992). It is the process of creating ideas while innovation is applying creative ideas (Rank, et al, 2004). creativity dimensions are the creative process, the creative

characters, the incubating environment and the tangible creative results (Al-Sulaibi, 2016).

According to (Sadler, 2015) Creativity Stages are (1) Preparation: By creating the right climate for this by learning a lot of skills. (2) Nursery: developing the solution to crystallize in completely mental relaxation. (3) Flash stage: the emergence of the spontaneous solution surprising the thinker himself. (4) Evaluation phase: to arbitrate the solution and the results of reason and logic.

2. Risk taking:

Al-Hakim and Ali (2017) say that writers and researchers agreed on risk as an essential dimension of entrepreneurship. Practicing business in uncertain and risky circumstances, risk appears when investing resources in a project with the probability of failure (Filser & Eggers, 2014) It is calculated controllable risk that was not kept for luck (Morris, et..al, 2008) Going into the unknown is a key feature for entrepreneurs (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003), It is an attempt to provide resources to the enterprise with a managed and calculated risk that may result in failure and costs (Zahra, 2017). It is necessary to calculate the risk arising from the business, The propensity to take risks varies from one institution to another depending on the nature of people, the environment, the organization and risk return (Tai ,2017). To classify entrepreneurs, Creativity and Risk taking were linked by (Landau, 1982,Hadrawi, 2011) into four types:

a. Entrepreneur = high creativity + high risk tolerance

b. Adventurer = low creativity + high risk tolerance

b. Supporter = low creativity + low risk tolerance

b. Dreamer = high creativity + low risk tolerance

3. Initiation:

It is a strategy that contributes to supporting the entrepreneurship and competitiveness of current and modern organizations (Mohammed, 2013) is the use of different methods and innovative ways to anticipate the needs and future environmental changes. The initiative reflects the entrepreneur's quest to be the number one contender in any recent development (Agrawal, 2017) is the pioneer for new opportunities that may or may not be consistent with the core of his current work (Anwar, 2018) and is the creation of change in the business sector with focus. High in creativity and innovation to surprise competitors Mint GAT & Services (Ratanapornsiri, 2003).

Quality of services:

The word "quality" is derived from the Latin word "qualitas", which refers to the nature and level of validity of the material ,which previously referred to as the accuracy of construction and mastery. Academics and specialists did not agree on a clear concept of quality. Definitions vary according to their application conditions (Elshaer, 2012, zikmund, 2003) Service is the change in the situation of a person or organization with their consent because of the activity of another organization (Hill, 1977), which, according to (Prakash and Mohanty, 2013) is intangible and heterogeneous, produced and used at the same time, and difficult to promote. Quality is the provision of a product or service that meets consumer satisfaction and expectations (Deming, 1988) it is the superiority in satisfying customer needs (Krajewski & pitzman, 1996), achieving customer satisfaction and expectations at a reasonable cost through efficient technical methods that guide workers and machines (Stevenson, 2002). Quality also is the level of satisfaction achieved by the service provided to the customer by meeting their needs and satisfying their desires (Lovelock and Wright, 1999).

The importance of quality of services in fierce competition stems from legal responsibility for compensatory damages, competing globally and locally can't be achieved without a good reputation and fame, customer protection groups have a big role in guiding customers to the best quality providers (Ali, 2016). The quality of hotel service is the first building block to achieve competitive advantage and continuity in the market in a rapidly changing environment. Below are forms of quality importance (Abubaker & Ali,2017):

1. The reputation of the hotel: An element that demonstrates the success of the hotel and reflects the confidence of current and future guests.

2. Competitive Advantage: Enhances the hotel's market share, through services beyond its competitors.

3. Customer Relationship: Adds value to the customer through a service that meets its requirements.

4. Customer loyalty: Happens when the guest comes back again and refuses the competitor's temptations.

Quality of Service Goals:

The three pillars of tourism (transport, accommodation and programs) are all hotel services serving the national economy. Hotels offer an environment that suits businesspeople where banks, libraries, shops, amenities and entertainment are located in one calm location (Abdelkader, 2001). Linking quality to service is to: (1) achieve guest satisfaction by meeting every customer customized need, (2) ensure that the customer enjoys his stay, (3) Making a profit, (4) Maintains a sustainable environment. Meanwhile despite the need for a big-budget, turning these objectives into goals is a necessity (Ahmed, 2017). The five service quality dimensions are Reliability, Response, Emphasis, Empathy and Tangibility (Ajarma, 2005, Bahi, 2016)

Quality of service measurement models:

Measuring the quality of service is difficult because of its intangible nature, Therefore, the most important measurement tools that were developed are:

1. SERVQUAL is an abbreviation of the word "Service Quality", in the model Parasurman used ten dimensions to measure quality, and then shortened them later to five (reliability, response, emphasis, empathy and tangibility), Subsequent studies have modified these dimensions repeatedly to suit the hotel sector. (Fowdar, 2007, Bouranta et al., 2009).

2. SERVPERF model is the result of combining the words "service" and "performance" that considers the quality of service as a measure of performance only, this model was firstly conducted by Cronin and Taylor in 1992 considering the actual perception of the customer service away from expectations. (Nassour et al., 2017) (Salah al-Din, 2016)

New trends in the assuring quality of services:

1. ISO 9000: To deliver services as actually required obligates organizations to define their products before production. The earlier ISO 9001 eliminated customer Satisfaction while ISO 9004 goes beyond to include the external client (Galon, 2003).

2. Benchmarking: Found in early 1980 but due to ignorance of its advantages it wasn't accepted until 1990 (Goetsch & Davis, 2014), It is an application of the best performance prevailing in the market, and is considered a point of reference to judge any activity or product in order to help organizations fix quality deviations (Abadi, 2010, Maryam, 2016).

3. Total quality management: Scientists did not agree on a clear definition of total quality management but they agreed on its aspects, Cohen and Brand defines TQM as the process of maintaining and improving the operations of the organization in order to develop quality that meets current and future consumer aspirations. (Abdullah, 2015)

The Federal Quality Institute has recognized TQM as producing optimum products guided with customers opinion (Idris and Al-Ghalbi, 2016), TQM works on (1) reducing and limiting customer complaints, (2) reducing costs (3) Raising market share, (4) Minimizing accidents and errors, (5) Raising consumer satisfaction, (6) Raising efficiency and performance (Hammoud, 2009).

13. Statistical analysis and results

Demographic characteristics

This section lists the demographic characteristics in two parts, the first of which is the gender, age, educational qualification, experience and the second demographic characteristics of the studied hotels.

Table (2): Frequencies of Demographic Variables

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	254	%77.4
	Female	74	%22.6
	Total	328	%100
Age	25 years and under	42	%12.8
	26-30 years	78	%23.8
	31-35 Year	92	%28.0
	36 years and over	116	%35.4
	Total	328	%100
Educational Qualification	Diploma or Less	88	%26.8
	Bachelor's degree	212	%64.6
	Master	20	%6.1
	Doctorate	8	%2.4
	Total	328	%100
Experience	5 Years and less	80	%24.4
	6 - 10 years	84	%25.6
	11-15 years	72	%22.0
	More than 15 years	92	%28.0
	Total	328	%100
Number of Hotel employees	less than 49	40	%12.2
	50-199 workers	104	%31.7
	(200) and more	184	%56.1
	Total	328	%100
Hotel age	(10) years and under	110	%33.5
	(11-15) years	32	%9.8
	(16-20) years	76	%23.2
	(21) years and above	110	%33.5
	Total	328	%100
Hotel Rating	Two stars and less	6	%1.8
	Three stars	18	%5.5
	Four stars	58	%17.7
	five stars	246	%75.0
	Total	328	%100

Table (2) shows the distribution of the sample according to the demographic factors as follows:

1. The study confirmed the statistics published by the Ministry of Tourism on the low representation of females in the society under study, where the proportion of females (23%) of the sample, while the number of males (77%). The researcher believes that the reason for this is the Jordanian culture that does not encourage the involvement of women in tourism work for many reasons, such as community view of the profession, and the wrong understanding of the nature of hotel work, although awareness of hotel work has begun early, but the role of women remained confined.
2. The percentage of holders of the bachelor's degree (65%) of the sample, which is proof that the hotels understudy keen to employ employees who have university degrees, in order to raise the quality of service.
3. It was noted that the response of the respondents about the years of experience was distributed almost equally on the four options, and this, according to the analysis of the researcher indicates the relative stability of the employees of the sector.

4. The share of the five-star hotels was the largest (75%) of the sample, and that's reasonable because these hotels according to the table (1) employ a big number of workers that represent (60%) of total sector employees.
5. The study indicated that (34%) of the hotels in question are newly constructed and (34%) have been around for twenty-one years. This means that the number of hotels has doubled and this, according to the researcher, is proof of the trend to encourage tourism in the previous period.

Descriptive analysis:

All the responses of the respondents were converted to degrees to find the mean and standard deviation for each field in the study as follow:

Table (3) Averages, Deviations and Rank of the Innovation

#	Questionnaire	Mean	Deviation	Rank	Rating
Q1.	The hotel provides a clear and announced strategy for all employees.	4.182	0.907	2	High
Q2.	Hotel management is constantly re-evaluating its organizational structure.	3.859	1.09	5	High
Q3.	The hotel is constantly updating its facilities.	4.164	0.791	3	High
Q4.	Hotel management engages employees in management decision-making.	3.463	1.097	6	Medium
Q5.	Hotel management is keen to stimulate employee innovation.	3.884	1.016	4	High
Q6.	The hotel management is keen to respond to the needs of its customers constantly.	4.518	0.649	1	High
Overall average of paragraphs		4.010	0.721	High	

According to the table (3), it was found that question number (6), which states: "The hotel management is keen to respond to the needs of its customers continuously" was of the highest arithmetic average. This can be explained by the fact that the hotel business does not provide a tangible product, but rather provides a service that measures its customer. Striving to satisfy the needs of the inmate is a major objective of the hotel sector. Paragraph (4), which states: "Hotel management engages employees in the management decision-making process" has been the weakest. This indicates that hotels are not aware of the effectiveness of involving employees at all levels in related tasks. Empowering and engaging employees contributes significantly to the excellence and development of the hotel industry.

Table (4) Averages, Deviations and Rank of the Creativity

#	Questionnaire	Mean	Deviation	Rank	Rating
Q7.	Hotel management takes advantage of the ideas of problem solvers.	3.993	0.808	1	High
Q8.	Hotel management encourages new employees' ideas at work.	3.932	0.878	3	High
Q9.	The management of the hotel delegates part of its powers to the various administrative levels.	3.969	0.845	2	High
Q10.	The hotel offers creative models from former employees.	3.622	1.068	6	Medium
Q11.	The hotel management is keen to apply innovative ideas and experiences constantly in the hotel operations.	3.872	0.906	4	High
Q12.	The hotel management seeks to attract innovators in the hotel sector to work.	3.835	0.913	5	High
Overall average of paragraphs		3.870	0.729	High	

The analysis of the arithmetic mean and the standard deviations of the questionnaire questions in the field of creativity strategy showed that paragraph (1), which states: "Hotel management benefits from the ideas of problem solvers" was of the highest arithmetic mean. Competition tools. Paragraph (4) reads: "The hotel offers

creative models from former employees." It was the weakest and this, according to the researcher weakens the demand for creativity, the creative person seeks to perpetuate his name, as well as an incentive for those who are coming to creativity.

Table (5) Averages, Deviations and Rank of the Risk taking

#	Questionnaire	Mean	Deviation	Rank	Rating
Q13.	The hotel can assess risks.	4.140	0.796	2	High
Q14.	Hotel management tends to take the risk of development.	3.872	0.899	3	High
Q15.	The hotel is looking for everything new in-service delivery.	4.317	0.803	1	High
Q16.	The hotel has funds for scientific research.	2.859	1.274	6	Medium
Q17.	The hotel management is able to challenge, insist and calculated risk.	3.707	1.001	4	High
Q18.	The hotel has scenarios to predict the surrounding risks	3.658	1.028	5	Medium
Overall average of paragraphs		3.870	0.763	High	

The analysis of the arithmetic mean and the standard deviations of the questionnaire questions in the field of risk strategy showed that paragraph (3), which states: "The hotel is looking for all that is new in service delivery" was the highest arithmetic average. Amman Hotels seeks to employ innovation, creativity and risk in new markets and modern services, customer expectations are growing and rising constantly and must be kept up. Paragraph (4) reads: "The hotel shall have a financial allowance for scientific research." It was the weakest, and this indicates that hotels are moving away from scientific research, unfortunately the researcher does not find awareness of the value of scientific research, although it will contribute to raising the quality of hotel services.

Table (6) Averages, Deviations and Rank of the initiation

#	Questionnaire	Mean	Deviation	Rank	Rating
Q19.	The hotel management cooperates with competitors.	3.597	1.070	2	High
Q20.	The management of the hotel is constantly changing its service operations.	3.945	0.851	3	High
Q21.	The hotel management is keen to pioneer in providing new services.	4.170	0.817	1	High
Q22.	The hotel is a race to embrace new business ideas.	3.878	0.969	6	Medium
Q23.	Hotel management seeks to seize opportunities.	4.164	0.744	4	High
Q24.	The hotel management is keen to use modern technologies.	4.067	0.828	5	Medium
Overall average of paragraphs		3.870	0.667	High	

The analysis of the arithmetic average and the standard deviations of the questionnaire questions in the field of innovation strategy showed that paragraph (3), which states: "The hotel management is keen to provide new services" was the highest arithmetic average, which is evidence that the hotel sector seeks to take a greater risk of the circumstances. In order to participate in solving future problems through the use of entrepreneurship strategies.

Paragraph (1) states: "The hotel management cooperates with competitors" was the lowest, but its average rating, which indicates the average perception of hotels in the Jordanian capital to the feasibility of containing the competitor, the researcher believes that competition does not mean hostility does not require love, too. Among the competitors promotes the achievement of the goals, which are common interests, cooperation does not diminish anyone, sometimes the competitor may have a solution to the problem faced by the hotel, and can make joint support agreements between competitors, this agreement may be reflected in a food product (such as fresh juices, ice cream) produced by a hotel distributed by Other hotels, or in pure means Common.

Table (7) Averages, Deviations and Rank of the Creativity

#	Questionnaire	Mean	Deviation	Rank	Rating
Q25.	The hotel enjoys a convenient location within easy reach.	4.591	0.603	4	High
Q26.	The hotel management provides a sophisticated communication system (Internet, telephone, fax, telex, etc.)	4.652	0.559	1	High
Q27.	The hotel management puts the best interests of the customer first.	4.628	0.627	2	High
Q28.	The hotel management is keen to provide the service with a high degree of accuracy to the customer.	4.530	0.648	6	High
Q29.	Staff at the hotel have enough knowledge of the customer's needs and desires.	4.329	0.782	8	High
Q30.	Staff is morale in dealing with hotel customers.	4.304	0.736	9	High
Q31.	The hotel plans are flexible.	4.018	0.860	10	High
Q32.	There is a constant willingness by the staff to meet the customers' demands at the hotel quickly.	4.372	0.709	7	High
Q33.	The hotel management is keen on the accuracy of its financial treatment with customers.	4.542	0.666	5	High
Q34.	Hotel management ensures the confidentiality of customer information.	4.615	0.736	3	High
Overall average of paragraphs		3.870	0.667	High	

The analysis of the arithmetic mean and the standard deviations of the questionnaire questions in the field of innovation strategy showed that paragraph (2), which states: "The hotel management provides a sophisticated communication system (Internet, telephone, fax, telex, etc.)" was the highest arithmetic average. Capital Hotels Amman provides advanced and comprehensive communications services and this is an indicator of the achievement of tangibility and is one of the dimensions of the quality of hotel services, which includes the environment of the apparent materials to the customer and a physical representation of the service.

Paragraph (7), which states: "Hotel plans are flexible" was the least average, and this indicates that hotels in the capital Amman and this indicator of sympathy are a dimension of the quality of hotel services is the extent of the customer's sense of being unique and understandable and sense of High level interest from the hotel staff in the capital Amman, empathy is an important dimension in the customer's appreciation of the level of quality of service.

Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA):

Used to verify the structural validity of the study scale to ensure that the study model matched its data (Hair et al, 2010), and according to the same source if 3 to 5 indicators are sufficient then data can proceed to the next stage Measurement Model (MM). results of variables were as follow:

A. CFA of Innovation

The significance values for assertive factor analysis were identical. Therefore, all questions were accepted without deletion, where the value of the square root index of the approximate error average (RMSEA) was (0.052) less than (0.08), the degree of freedom (9) was greater than zero, and the value of the measure of independence (square Kai) is equal to (16.798), dividing the square of Kai by the degree of freedom produces the alternative standard square kai whose value is (1.866) which is less than (5). The comparative conformity index (CFI) was greater than (0.90) where it reached (0.991), which means similarity between the model and the data.

B. CFA of the Creativity

After the fourth question was deleted, all the questions were accepted, the significance values of the assertive

factor analysis were identical, the value of the square root of the approximate mean error (RMSEA) was (0.030) less than (0.08), the degree of freedom (2) was greater than zero, and was the value of the measure of independence (kai square) is equal to (2.593). The comparative conformity index (CFI) was greater than (0.90) where it reached (0.997), which means similarity between the model and the data.

C. CFA of Risk Strategy

The significance values for assertive factor analysis were identical. Therefore, all questions were accepted without deletion, where the value of the square root of the approximate error average (RMSEA) was (0.077) less than (0.08), the degree of freedom (9) was greater than zero, and the value of the measure of independence (square Kai) was equal to (26.253), dividing the square of Kai by the degree of freedom produces the alternative standard square kai whose value is (2.917) and is less than (5). The comparative conformity index (CFI) was greater than (0.90) where it reached (0.981), which means similarity between the model and the data.

D) CFA of the Initiative

The significance values for assertive factor analysis were identical. Accordingly, all questions were accepted after the first question was deleted, where the RMSEA value was (0.000) less than (0.08), the degree of freedom (5) was greater than zero, and the value of the measure of independence (square kai) Is equal to (4.123), dividing the square of Kai by the degree of freedom produces the alternative standard square kai whose value is (0.825) which is less than (5). The comparative conformity index (CFI) was greater than (0.90) where it reached (1.000), which means a perfect match between the model and the data.

E. CFA Quality Of Serves

The significance values for assertive factor analysis were identical. Therefore, all the questions were accepted after the first question was deleted, where the approximate error of the square root of RMSEA was 0.077 less than 0.08, the degree of freedom 22 was greater than zero, and the value of the measure of independence (square kai)) Is equal to (64.823), dividing the square of Kai by the degree of freedom produces the alternative standard square kai whose value is (2.947) which is less than (5). The comparative conformity index (CFI) was greater than (0.90) where it reached (0.977), which means an almost perfect match between the model and the data.

Test the normal distribution of data:

Natural state distribution analysis is a vital test used as an indicator to estimate the normal distribution of the data collected. It is necessary to test the normal state before performing the regression test (Hair et al, 1998). The results showed that Skew deviation values range between (0.448) and (1.768) which fall within the recommended value ± 3 , while kurtosis values range between (0.721) and (4.697) which fall within the recommended value ± 7 (Hair Consequently, all elements in this study follow the normal distribution curve.

Measurement Model (MM)

Figure 2 Measurement Model (MM)

Figure 2 shows that after the omission of the third question of the third dimension and the tenth question of the dependent variable, the value of the square root of the approximate error average (RMSEA) is equal to (0.057) less than (0.08), and the degree of freedom (309) is greater than zero.

The value of the measure of independence (kai square) was equal to (640.948), by dividing the square of Kai by the degree of freedom, the standard square of kai is substituted (2.074) and is less than (5). The comparative conformity index (CFI) was greater than (0.90) where it reached (0.948), which means an almost perfect match between the model and the data. In this model there are more than 3 identical indicators and assertive factor analysis is acceptable if 3 to 5 identical indicators (Hair et al, 1998), the model is therefore suitable for the next stage of hypothesis analysis.

Structural Equation Modeling (SME)

Figure 3 The (SEM) of strategic entrepreneurship dimensions and quality of services

The RMSEA value was 0.073 less than 0.08, the freedom degree was 309 greater than zero, and the independence scale (kai square) was 850.165, dividing the square kai by Liberty produces the alternative Kai square, which is 2.751 and is less than 5, Therefore the SEM model is fit.

Hypotheses discussion and results:

Table (8) Hypotheses results

Hypothesis Result	P-value	C.R.	Standardized Estimate	Unstandardized Estimate		Path
			Beta	S. E	Estimate	
H0 significant	0.001	10.337	0.743***	.035	.362	ES → QS
H0 ₁ significant	0.001	-1.074	0.362***	1.284	5.857	IN → QS
H0 ₂ significant	0.001	0.371	0.298***	.064	.208	CR → QS
H0 ₃ significant	0.001	3.181	0.308***	.048	.153	RT → QS
H0 ₄ significant	0.003	-2.973	-0.232**	.040	-.120	IV → QS

Notes: *Sig. at p< 0.050; ** Sig. at p< 0.010; *** Sig. at p< 0.001. (Two-tailed)

- The study found that R=74% and that means Strategic entrepreneurship (innovation, creativity, Risk taking, Proactiveness) and quality of service are related, and that strategic entrepreneurship explains 55% of the change in the quality of service. And since P=Value is below 0.05 we reject the negative hypothesis and accept the alternative one, "There is a statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level

($\alpha=0.05$) for Strategic Entrepreneurship with its dimensions (innovation, creativity, risk, initiative) on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels". This result agrees with (Al-Taie,2017) and (Zahra, 2017) who demonstrated the importance of strategic entrepreneurship in enhancing the quality of outputs for sustainable competition.

2. The study found that $R=36\%$ and that means that innovation strategy and quality of service are related, and that innovation strategy explains 45% of the change in the quality of service. And since $P=$ Value is below 0.05 we reject the negative hypothesis and accept the alternative one "There is a statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the innovation strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels". This result agrees with (Crossan & Apaydin, 2010) and (Anning-dorson,2016) that assures the importance of innovation in the competitive environment as a dimension of entrepreneurship.
3. The study found that $R=29.8\%$ and that means that creative strategy and quality of service are related, and that creativity strategy explains 45% of the change in the quality of service. And since $P=$ Value is below 0.05 we reject the negative hypothesis and accept the alternative one " There is a statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the creativity strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels". This result agrees with (Al-Hadrawi & Al-Kalabi, 2013) that assure the importance of creative strategy in enhancing the quality of service.
4. The study found that $R=30.8\%$ and that means that risk-taking strategy and quality of service are related, and that risk-taking strategy explains 45% of the change in the quality of service. And since $P=$ Value is below 0.05 we reject the negative hypothesis and accept the alternative one " There is a statistically significant impact at the statistical significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) for the risk-taking strategy on the quality of hotel services in Amman hotels". This result agrees with (Al-Kamri & Sefr, 2017) that assures the importance of risk strategy in enhancing product quality.
5. The study found that there is a statistically significant impact equal to (-0.232), at the statistical significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the initiative strategy on the quality of hotel services, and that initiative strategy explains 45% of the change in the quality of service. a negative relationship, that is, when the standard deviation increases by one integer to the strategy of the initiative, the quality of hotel services will be reduced by (0.232). The study thinks that this is due to the difficult economic conditions that the region is going through, and initiation is influenced by external forces and the internal environment.

Study Recommendations:

Following are recommendations that are believed to be useful in raising the quality of hotel services using strategic entrepreneurship:

1. Engaging and empowering workers in decision-making processes is needed to improve the quality of service offered to customers. Empowered employees are more productive, loyal, and committed.
2. Providing innovative models of former employees who have previously contributed successes, that will motivate workers and employees to put their names in the history of his firm.
3. The study stressed the need to provide research and development allocations to face systematic and nonsystematic risks. R&D is essential for organizational entrepreneurship process, it guides the innovation by transforming capabilities into products and services.
4. The study develops conceptual plans and scenarios for surrounding risks that may face hotels, it improves the ability to go and react. Planning improves coordination between individuals, units and activities. Planning also improves time management and helps in achieving goals.
5. It is encouraging cooperation with competitors in the sector. This may be to share target groups for integration, or by using a common hotel product. Competitors may have complementary strengths that enable the sharing of gains.
6. The study recommends intensifying studies on the variables of the current study to cover the entire hotel sector in all parts of the Kingdom, and to concentrate on raising the research efforts on this active sector.

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